

Place and Basis for the Formation of Meteorological Vocabulary in the System of French and Uzbek Languages

Khamidova Muborak Khafizovna

Professor of the Department of French Philology, Doctor of sciences (DSc)

Yuldosheva Mohinur

Graduate student of Bukhara State University

Abstract: Metonyms are usually widely used in the field of science “meteorology”. Meteorology is the name of the science that studies the atmosphere and climate, and specialists involved in this are called “meteorologists”. Meteorologists are involved in weather forecasting. Explaining the nature of various phenomena occurring in the atmosphere: winds, cyclones, anticyclones and other similar processes is one of the main tasks of meteorologists.

Keywords: metonym, phenomena, the nature, cyclone, meteorology, the earth.

INTRODUCTION

Man, in the process of perceiving and understanding the surrounding world, the picture of the world, tried not only to study weather phenomena, but also to name, describe and evaluate them. As a result, all this knowledge began to be reflected in natural language with the help of special lexical units – metonyms.

“Metonym” refers to words denoting the state and structure of the atmosphere, the circulation of heat and moisture in the atmosphere and on the surface of the earth, thermal regime, movement of the atmosphere and its parts, as well as electrical, acoustic and optical phenomena in the atmosphere. They are also called “metonyms”.

Metonyms are usually widely used in the field of science “meteorology”. Meteorology is the name of the science that studies the atmosphere and climate, and specialists involved in this are called “meteorologists”. Meteorologists are involved in weather forecasting. Explaining the nature of various phenomena occurring in the atmosphere: winds, cyclones, anticyclones and other similar processes is one of the main tasks of meteorologists.

METHODOLOGY

The term “meteor” actually comes from the Greek word “wttewpov,” which means “celestial and aerial phenomenon.” It was used in German in the seventeenth century. In the 17th-18th centuries, it also became widely used in the Russian language and denoted any weather phenomenon. Airborne phenomena or meteorites are real phenomena that occur in the air and persist in the environment for some time.

They can be felt and understood only through feelings. They are usually fiery or watery... For example, water meteors are fog, clouds, rain, dew, frost, snow, hail.

The word “meteor” fully retained the meaning indicated in the 19th century. Let’s say, from the point of view of meteorology, clouds are “systems of water vapor condensation products stopped in the atmosphere (not close to

surface of the Earth) - drops of water or ice crystals, or both, that is, nothing more than cloud elements. As the cloud's size increases, elements and their falling speed increase, they fall out of the cloud as precipitation. It is the presence of this cloudiness that is inextricably linked to the likelihood of subsequent precipitation, which in turn leads to the difference.

METHODS AND RESULTS

People have long been interested in weather predictions. Each nation has its own experience in this regard. In the process, metonymyms were also formed in each vernacular language. Initially, this process proceeded spontaneously, but gradually acquired a scientific essence.

In particular, by the 19th century, meteorology was recognized as a separate science. For example, in Russia they first began to study weather in the 17th century. From the second half of the 17th century, the network of meteorological stations was expanded.

Climatology is the name of the science of climate, which in Uzbek is called “iqlimshunoslik”

CONCLUSION

Words related to it are considered climatonyms. Climatology is one of the geographical sciences, since climatology studies the totality of its inherent atmospheric conditions depending on the geographical location of the territories.

Climatology is closely related to meteorology. Because the study of natural and social factors causing climate change, as well as the influence of human agricultural and industrial activities on it, constitutes the main tasks of climatology.

Since the laws of climate can be understood on the basis of the general laws that govern atmospheric processes, in analyzing the causes of the occurrence of different types of climate and their distribution throughout the world, climate science starts from the concepts and laws of meteorology.

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